

Metal Chelates of Tetradentate Ligands derived from 1,2,3-Triketone-2-phenylhydrazones and Diamines

V. T. REMA, K. KRISHNANKUTTY* and JOHNS MICHAEL

Department of Chemistry, University of Calicut, Kerala-673 635

Manuscript received 5 May 1995, revised 9 February 1996, accepted 14 February 1996

In continuation of our studies on polydentate and macrocyclic ligand systems¹ we report here the synthesis of a series of dibasic tetradentate (N_4) chelating ligands (1) and their Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} chelates (2). The ligands were prepared by the condensation of 2-phenylhydrazones of 1,3-diketones (acetylacetone, benzoylacetone and 1,3-cyclohexanedione) with diamines (1,2-diaminoethane, 1,3-diaminopropane and 1,6-diaminohexane).

M = Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Pd^{II}

1

n R = R_1 = CH_3 R = CH_3 , R_1 = C_6H_5 R = R_1 = $-(CH_2)_3$

2 H_2pae H_2pbe H_2pce

3 H_2pap H_2pbp H_2pcyp

6 H_2pah H_2pbh H_2peyh

Results and Discussion

Analytical data of the ligands show that one equivalent of the diamine reacts with two equivalents of the hydrazone. IR spectra of all the compounds (Table 1) show three strong bands in the region 1 610–1 800 cm^{-1} , which can be assigned^{1,2} to the stretching of free conjugated R_1CO , the hydrazone $C=N$ and the imine $C=N$ functions of structure 1. A medium intensity band at $\sim 1 525 cm^{-1}$ due to NH deformation is observed in the spectra of all the compounds. That the acidic protons are involved in strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding is evident from the presence of a broad band at 3 500–2 400 cm^{-1} .

TABLE I—SPECTRAL DATA OF THE LIGANDS

Compd.	M.p. °C	ν_{max} (cm^{-1})			δ (ppm)			
		C=O	C=N	C-N	NH	Aryl	$(CH_2)_n$	$CH_3/(CH_2)_3$
H_2pae	70	1 670	1 620, 1 615	1 280	14.85	0.80–7.35	3.85	2.55
H_2pap	65	1 675	1 622, 1 616	1 282	14.75	6.80–7.35	3.53 3.45 3.38	2.55 2.65 2.70
H_2pah	108	1 668	1 628, 1 618	1 278	13.65	6.50–7.35	3.12	2.50
H_2pbe	76	1 646	1 620, 1 614	1 275	14.35	6.80–7.30	3.82	2.75
H_2pbp	98	1 642	1 620, 1 614	1 272	14.10	6.80–7.30 7.45–7.80	3.56 3.48	2.78
H_2pbh	138	1 640	1 620, 1 615	1 280	15.40	6.80–7.30 7.40–7.80	3.34 3.08	2.72 2.17
H_2pce	141	1 672	1 628, 1 618	1 288	15.47	7.24–7.58	3.58	2.18 2.72
H_2pcp	222	1 677	1 625, 1 616	1 285	14.07	7.26–7.65	3.20 3.60	2.10 2.55 2.65
H_2pch	242	1 675	1 625, 1 615	1 282	13.72	7.26–7.67	3.42 3.72	2.15 2.71

The ^1H nmr spectra of the compounds are characterised by the presence of a low field slightly broadened two-proton signal at ~ 15 ppm due to the chelated hydrazone protons²⁻⁴. Proton on a nitrogen can effect spin-spin splitting of protons on an adjacent carbon. Thus if the protons are attached to the imine nitrogens, the resonance signals of the adjacent methylene group should split further. However, in the spectra of all the compounds, no such splitting was observed, thereby eliminating the possible azo tautomeric form of the compounds. The position and integrated intensities of all the protons (Table 1) agree well with structure 1. In agreement with the structure, the ^{13}C nmr spectrum of H_2pae shows signals due to two methyl groups at 18.153 and 27.109 ppm, one C=O group at 198.278 ppm, two C=N 163.781 and 145.390 ppm, and one C-N function 48.107 ppm. The phenyl carbon signals are observed at 115.257, 124.528, 128.950, 132.087 ppm.

Further evidence for the structures of the compounds is obtained from the mass spectra. The spectra are characterised by an intense molecular ion peak $\text{P}^+(\text{P} + 1)^+$. All compounds showed a prominent peak due to (P-92). Its formation can be explained only with structure 1 in which the cleavage of $\text{P}^+(\text{P} + 1)^+$ occurs first at one of the N-N bonds with the elimination of $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH}^+$ (m/z 92). Such a cleavage is typical of phenylhydrazones of 1,3-diketones^{1,5}. Other important peaks are due to the elimination of RCO, R_1CO from P^+ and (P-92)⁺ ions.

Metal chelates: Analytical and molecular weight data show 1 : 1 metal-to-ligand stoichiometry for the metal complexes (the observed values are within 1% of the theoretical values). The Cu^{II} complexes show a normal magnetic moment (~ 1.78 B M.) and the Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes are diamagnetic. Conductivity data indicate that all the complexes are non-ionic.

The ir spectra of the complexes clearly indicate that the carbonyl groups are not involved in bonding with the metal ion and the hydrazone and imine nitrogens are engaged in chelate formation. Thus the $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ band of the free ligand remained almost unchanged in the spectra of all complexes, but the $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ bands shifted appreciably to lower values (~ 10 cm^{-1}). The band at ~ 1525 cm^{-1} (NH) of the free ligand is absent in the spectra of all the chelates. The broad ligand band at 3500–2400 cm^{-1} cleared up in the spectra of all the chelates, which indicates that the hydrogen bonded protons of 1 are replaced by metal ion. Two medium intensity bands, not found in the free ligand, appeared at ~ 550 cm^{-1} in the spectra of all the chelates, presumably due to $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$.

In the ^1H nmr spectra of the Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes, the low field signal due to the N-H protons disappeared indicating the replacement of the chelated proton by metal ion as in structure 2. Observed position and integrated intensity of the ^1H nmr signals of the chelates conform to

their formulation as in structure 2. The ^{13}C nmr spectrum of the $\text{Ni}(\text{pae})$ indicates that the hydrazone nitrogens and the imine nitrogens are involved in bonding with metal ion. Thus the imine carbon signal of the ligand shifted from 145.390 to 153.594 ppm in the complex and the phenyl carbon signal at 132.087 shifted to 152.630 ppm. All other signals suffered only minor shift in the complex.

The FAB mass spectra of the Cu^{II} chelates are in accord with structure 2. The spectra show intense molecular ion peak corresponding to the [ML] stoichiometry. Elimination of fragments like C_6H_5 , RCO, R_1CO are typical of all the spectra. Several metal-containing fragments are observed in the low mass region of the spectra. Thus the results indicate that the ligands function as tetradentate N_4 donor (2). Formation of similar complexes of H_2pae was reported earlier⁶ through the diazo coupling of metal complexes of Schiff bases derived from acetylacetone and 1,2-diamines.

Experimental

Phenylhydrazones of the 1,3-diketones (1,2,3-triketone-2-phenylhydrazones) were prepared⁷. The condensation reaction was carried out as follows. A methanolic solution (15 ml) of the diamine (0.01 mol) was added to a solution of the phenylhydrazone (0.02 mol) in methanol (25 ml). The solution was stirred for ~ 4 h and then evaporated at reduced pressure. The resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from hot methanol.

The Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes were prepared by the following a general procedure. A solution of the metal salt (0.01 mol) in methanol (20 ml) was added to a hot ($\sim 60^\circ$) solution of the ligand (0.01 mol) in methanol (20 ml). The mixture was stirred for ~ 1 h and then evaporated to half of its volume on a paraffin bath at $\sim 70^\circ$. The precipitated complex was washed with water and dried under reduced pressure.

References

1. K. KRISHNANKUTTY and M. JOHNS, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1991, 22, 327; 1993, 24, 259; *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1995, 34, 299; K. KRISHNANKUTTY and V. T. REMA, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal Org. Chem.*, 1995, 25, 243.
2. A. MITCHELL and D. C. NONHEBEL, *Tetrahedron*, 1979, 35, 2013.
3. M. G. B. DREW, B. VICKERY and G. R. WILLEY, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1982, 1279.
4. A. LYCKA, J. JIRMAN and A. CEE, *Magn. Res. Chem.*, 1990, 28, 408.
5. K. KOBAYASHI and K. HIROSE, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1972, 45, 1700, 3551.
6. K. P. BALAKRISHNAN and V. KRISHNAN, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Organic Chem.*, 1978, 8, 227.
7. K. H. SAUNDERS and R. L. M. ALLEN, "Aromatic Diazo Compounds", 3rd. ed., Edward Arnold, London, 1985; S. M. PARMETER, *Org. React.*, 1959, 10, 1.